

Kinetics of the Acid-Catalysed Hydrolysis of 2 : 4-Dihydroxy-Acetophenone Isonicotinoyl Hydrazone

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The rate of acid-catalysed hydrolysis of 2 : 4-dihydroxy acetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone in aqueous methanol at 30° showed linear response to the molar concentrations of hydrochloric acid (0.01-0.1 M). Plot of log k vs log [HCl] indicated the participation of one hydrogen ion in the rate determining step. The activation energy (15.3 kcal mole⁻¹) and entropy of activation (-25.6 cal mole⁻¹ K⁻¹) point out that the reaction is bimolecular. The effect of methanol content and added neutral salt proves that the hydrazone is hydrolysed by A-2 mechanism with a nucleophilic attack of water on the protonated substrate. Effect of Cu(II) resulted in the formation of copper-substrate complex which is hydrolysed more difficulty than the free substrate.

ISONICOTINOYL hydrazones of carbonyl compounds were used as analytical reagents¹ in acid media. A survey of the literature however revealed that not much work was done on the kinetics of acid hydrolysis of the hydrazones. The present paper describes the results obtained in the hydrolysis of 2 : 4-dihydroxy acetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone which is also known as resacetophenone isoniazid hydrazone (RPINH) in presence of hydrochloric acid. This particular substrate is chosen because it is extensively used in acid media as an analytical reagent in our laboratory.

Experimental

Materials : RPINH was prepared by the procedure similar to that adopted for preparing *o*-hydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone². Standard methods reported in literature were employed for the purification of chemicals wherever it was necessary. All the solutions were made in conductivity water. Stock solutions ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) of RPINH, resacetophenone (RP) and isonicotinoyl hydrazide (INH) were prepared in methanol.

The absorption spectra of 50% aqueous methanolic solutions of RPINH, RP and INH in appropriate HCl solution were recorded immediately after mixing and after 24 hrs against a blank containing the solvent and the acid. Typical spectra in 0.01 M HCl are presented in Fig. 1. These spectra reveal that the absorbance of RPINH decreased considerably with time and after about 24 hrs it is almost equal to the sum of the absorbances of RP and INH (the expected products). This indicates that the substrate is hydrolysed into RP and INH and there is no back formation of the hydrazone. No change was however observed in the spectra of RP or INH even after 24 hrs and this suggests that these are not undergoing any change under the experimental conditions.

The reaction is monitored spectrophotometrically under pseudo first-order conditions by following the disappearance of RPINH. The rate

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 50% aqueous methanolic solutions of resacetophenone isoniazid hydrazone (Curve A), Resacetophenone isoniazid hydrazone after 24 hours (Curve B), Resacetophenone (Curve C) and Isoniazid Hydrazide (Curve D). [HCl]=0.01 M.

constants were computed from log (absorbance) vs time plots. A typical plot is presented in Fig. 2. Reported rate constants (k) are reproducible to $\pm 4\%$.

The results relating to the effect of different factors on the rate of hydrolysis are presented in the Tables 1 to 5.

Results and Discussion

Effect of acid : It is seen from the values of the rate constants (k) at different concentrations of HCl (Table 1) that the rate increased linearly with

molarity of HCl. Plot of log k vs log [HCl] is linear with a slope of approximately one, indicating that one hydrogen ion is participating in the rate determining step. Assuming that 0.025 M HCl, HClO₄ and CH₃.CO₂H, 0.0125 M H₂SO₄ and 0.0083 M H₃PO₄ are completely ionised to give a

Fig. 2. Plot of log absorbance vs time. [HCl]=0.1 M; Temp.=30°; Solvent=50% aqueous methanol.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF HCl IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF KCl [RPINH]=2×10⁻⁴M; μ=0.1M; Temp=30°

[HCl] (M)	[KCl] (M)	Rate constant (K)	
		In presence of KCl 10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)	In absence of KCl 10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)
0.010	0.030	2.6	1.6
0.025	0.075	6.1	4.5
0.050	0.050	9.3	10.8
0.075	0.025	16.0	16.1
0.100	0.000	21.0	21.0

TABLE 2—Rate Constant (k) in Presence of Different Acids at 30°

Acid	[HClO ₄]	[HCl]	H ₂ SO ₄	H ₃ PO ₄	CH ₃ .CO ₂ H
pH	1.60	1.65	2.20	2.70	3.70
10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)	4.7	4.5	1.5	0.7	0.03

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF METHANOL ON THE RATE CONSTANT (k)

[HCl]=0.025M;		Temp=30°				
Vol-% MeOH		20	30	40	50	60
Dielectric constant		69.75	65.00	61.50	57.25	52.75
10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)		12.9	9.6	6.3	4.5	3.4

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF KCl CONCENTRATION

[RPINH]=2×10 ⁻⁴ M;		[HCl]=0.025M					Temp=30°	
[KCl] (M)		0.000	0.135	0.250	0.375	0.500	0.625	
10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)		4.5	6.0	6.5	7.3	8.1	8.5	

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF [Cu(II)][EDTA] AND [Cu(II)]+[EDTA] ON THE RATE

[RPINH]=2×10⁻⁴M; [HCl]=0.025M; Temp=30°

[CuSO ₄] or [EDTA] mM	Rate constants in presence of		
	Cu(II) 10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)	EDTA 10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)	Cu(II)+EDTA 10 ⁴ k(S ⁻¹)
0.00	4.5	—	—
0.01	4.0	4.2	4.6
0.10	3.1	4.8	4.3
0.16	2.3	4.8	4.3
0.20	2.2	—	—
0.22	1.9	—	—
0.24	1.8	—	—
0.28	1.8	—	—

hydrogen ion concentration of 2.5×10⁻²M, the rate constants are determined in presence of these acids (cf. Table 2). The practical determination of pH of these acid solutions however revealed that the [H₃O⁺] is not the same. The observed rate change is thus found to be due to the change in pH. This suggests that the anion of the acid at these low concentrations is not playing a role. Plot of log k vs pH gave a straight line with a unit slope, which confirms that one proton is involved in the rate limiting step.

Effect of temperature: Rate constant was determined at 30°, 35° and 40° and the activation parameters were calculated graphically. These values 15.3 k. cal mole⁻¹ (ΔE*) and -25.6 cal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ (ΔS*) point out that the reaction is bimolecular.

Effect of methanol: The rate decreased with increase of methyl alcohol content (Table 3) and plot of log k vs 1/D gave a straight line with negative slope (Fig. 3). According to Amis^{3,4} treatment this means that the reaction is between a negative ion and a dipole. Plot of k vs (mole fraction) of water gave a straight line with a positive slope. This suggests that water is participating in the reaction and the reaction is A-2 type. The acid dependence of the rate showed that the protonated

Fig. 3. Plot of log k vs 1/D. Effect of methanol, [HCl]=0.025 M; Temp.=30°.

substrate is involved in the rate limiting step. It is therefore concluded that the reaction is of A-2 type involving a positive ion and a dipole and that the negative slope of Amis plot is a deviation. The rate data is best explained by Elsemongy's equation⁶ confirming that the sign of the slope obtained in Amis plot is only a deviation.

Effect of added neutral salt : The rate data presented in Table 4 reveals that the added neutral salt exerted a positive effect on the rate of hydrolysis.

Effect of copper(II) : The rate decreased with increase in the concentration of cupric ions till the latter is equal to the substrate concentration (Table 5). The decrease is therefore attributed to the complexation of copper with the substrate. The formation of 1 : 1 complex between the metal ion and the substrate is confirmed by the Job's method⁶ carried out at 500 nm (λ_{\max} of the complex). The results presented in Table 5 show that the rate increased on adding EDTA to a solution containing the substrate and copper ions. The rate constant in presence of equal concentrations of copper and EDTA is the same as that obtained in the absence of both. This proves that the rate decrease on the addition of Cu(II) is due to the formation of slowly

hydrolysable copper-substrate complex. The resistance of the complex to hydrolysis is attributed to the bicyclic ring structure of the complex.

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